

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF NATURAL COUMARINS ISOLATED FROM *LUVANGA SCANDENS*, HAM

BY PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND (MISS) ASIMA MOOKERJEE

The berries of *Luvanga scandens* Ham. (Family *Rutaceae*) are sold in the bazzars of Bengal under the name of Káklá. They are an important constituent of the "Group of eight remedies" of the Ayurvedic system of medicine, according to which 'the root and berries are sweet, oily and cooling; allay thirst; cure consumption and biliousness; aggravate kapha.' They are further used for preparing a perfumed medicinal oil.

The rinds of the berries contain numerous oily glands, the oil of which is more or less stimulating, tonic and fragrant.

The present paper describes the constituents of the berries which were procured from the local market. These were identified by Prof. A. Das-Gupta of the Bangabasi College, Calcutta, to whom our best thanks are due.

The crushed berries on extraction with petroleum ether gave a greenish brown oil from which four crystalline neutral compounds have been isolated. No alkaloid could be detected in the berries. It should be mentioned in this connection that only the *matured fruits yield the compounds described below but these are totally absent in unripe samples.*

(1) A colourless compound, m.p. 145° , crystallising in long, slender, colourless needles, was obtained in a yield of 0.1-0.4%. It is neutral to litmus, indifferent towards ferric chloride and shows no optical activity. It is insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali, but dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a stable yellow colour. An alcoholic solution of the substance turns yellow on the addition of aqueous alkali, and the alkaline solution remains clear on dilution with water. Acidification precipitates the original substance, thus apparently the substance behaves like a coumarin.

The analytical data are found to agree with the formula $C_{11}H_8O_3(OMe)$. The properties of the compound as also the observed analytical values indicate agreement with those of xanthotoxin(I) which was first isolated from *Fagara xanthoxyloides*, Lam (Thoms, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1910, 34, 1279) and later on from *Ruta chalepensis*, Linn (Brandt, *Dissertation, Berlin*, 1915).

The identity of compound (I) with xanthotoxin could be definitely established by a direct comparison and the mixed m.p. of the two substances, an authentic specimen of xanthotoxin being received from Professor E. Spáth of Vienna, to whom our best thanks are due.

(2) The second substance, m.p. 128° , forms stout, rhombic plates and is obtained in a yield of 0.05-0.06%. It gives orange-red colour with cold concentrated sulphuric acid. The compound is neutral and indifferent towards ferric chloride. It is insoluble in aqueous alkali but dissolves in alcoholic potassium hydroxide from which the original substance is precipitated by acidification. Thus it behaves as a coumarin.

The observed C-H values and molecular weight agree with the formula $C_{14}H_{12}O_2$. It is optically inactive and does not contain any methoxy group. We thought that the compound might be identical with xanthyletin (II) which has been isolated so far only from *Xanthoxylum americanum*, Mill (Robertson and Subramaniam, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 286; Bell and Robertson, *ibid.*, 1936, 1828; Dieterle and Kruta, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1937, 275, 45).

The tetrahydro derivative of the coumarin has been prepared by catalytic hydrogenation with palladium-charcoal, and the reduction product, thus obtained, is found to have the same m.p. 158.5° as tetrahydroxanthyletin and both of them show no depression in their mixed melting points. The identity of the second compound of *L. scandens*, with xanthyletin has been established under the joint investigation with Späth and Dobrovolny (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1450).

(3) The third neutral substance melts at 151.52° and has the formula $C_{11}H_8O_4(OMe)_2$. This is supposed to be a coumarin derivative from its behaviour and properties. A close inspection of the properties of this compound suggests its identity with *isopimpinellin* (III) (Hent, *Arch. Pharm.* 1898, 236, 162; Wessely and Kallab, *Monatsh*, 1932, 59, 16). A direct comparison has been made between the two substances, *isopimpinellin* being obtained

from *Pimpinella saxifraga*. The properties of the two compounds are identical and a mixture of the two also melts at 151.52° .

(4) The fourth compound (yield 0.08-0.5%) is a new substance and has been named "luvangetin." It forms colourless plates, m.p. $108-109^\circ$. It could be obtained pure with considerable difficulty (*vide* experimental). The method of purification consists in slow crystallisation of the crude substance and subsequent separation of luvangetin from other constituents by hand-picking.

The C-H values and the molecular weight show that luvangetin has the formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$. Methoxy estimation by Zeisel-Pregl-Vieböck's method proves the presence of one methoxy group. On the catalytic hydrogenation with palladium-charcoal, luvangetin gives a dihydrocoumarin, m.p. 131° , having the formula $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$. Luvangetin is optically inactive and is found to share many of the properties of coumarin. It is neutral to litmus, but dissolves in alcoholic potassium hydroxide with a yellow colour. The substance is precipitated from the alcoholic solution on acidification, but not on dilution with water. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with an orange-red colour. The formula of luvangetin therefore can be written as (IV). Since luvangetin does not respond to acetylation or tests for the ketonic group, OH or CO group may be assumed to be absent. The insolubility of luvangetin in dilute aqueous potassium hydroxide and its indifference towards ferric chloride prove the absence of a phenolic OH group in the molecule. In the absence of any direct proof of the function of the fourth oxygen atom, it is assumed to be of the ether type.

The analytical data of luvangetin and its properties suggested at first its identity with peucedanin (Jassoy and Haensel, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1898, 236, 661) (V).

But a close inspection of the properties of luvangetin, however, revealed that it is different from peucedanin. The latter is easily demethylated by means of concentrated hydrochloric acid at room temperature to oreoselon (VI) (Späth, Kläger and Schlösser, *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2207) whereas luvangetin remains unchanged under similar experimental conditions.

The C_3H_7O residue might originate from isoprene molecule. Many natural coumarins have been proved to be condensation products of isoprene with substituted coumarins. The isoprene unit might be present in various forms, the possible types of which are represented by the following :

Of these the first type is out of consideration in the present case, since coumarins containing phenoxy groups, $Me_2C=CH-CH_2O-$ get readily hydrolysed by concentrated sulphuric acid in glacial acetic acid into phenolic compounds (Späth and Kläger, *Ber.*, 1933, **66**, 920).

Luvangetin under similar experimental conditions does not give any phenolic substance. Like other furocoumarins (e.g., Imperatorin, *vide supra*) luvangetin does not give rise to furan-2 : 3-dicarboxylic acid on oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide, and therefore it does not contain any unsubstituted furan ring.

Glycide ring structure for luvangetin, as shown in type (iii) is quite unlikely as the molecular formula in that case would become $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ in place of $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$: the observed

C-H values, however, agree better with the latter formula. Moreover, a compound of the type (iii) would be expected to undergo hydrolysis to a dihydroxy compound by means of aqueous oxalic acid (Späth and Klager, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 914).

Type (ii) and (iv) might suggest a possible solution of the constitution of luvangetin.

It has been settled in a joint work with Späth and his co-workers (*Ber.*, 1940, 73B, 1361) that luvangetin has the structure of type (iv) (e.g. VII) and this has been definitely confirmed by its synthesis (Späth and Schmid, *Ber.*, 1941, 74B, 103).

EXPERIMENTAL

Test for Alkaloid.—60 G. of the crushed berries were extracted with rectified spirit in a Soxhlet for 15 hours. The extract was freed from the solvent under reduced pressure and the residue poured into 1% acetic acid solution (200 c.c.). The mixture was extracted with ether and its aqueous portion filtered. The clear filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia and extracted with ether. Removal of ether left a trace of oily matter which did not give appreciable precipitate with acidified potassium bismuth iodide solution.

Isolation of the Coumarins.—Matured berries (2.5 kg) of *L. scandens* were crushed in a mortar with purified sand. The mixture was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) for 24 hours in a Soxhlet. The product was allowed to stand overnight and then filtered to remove a crystalline deposit and tarry matters (Fraction P). The clear filtrate was freed from the solvent on the water-bath and the brown syrupy liquid was allowed to stand in a cool place for about a week. The crystals (Fraction Q) which separated out were collected and washed with petroleum ether and dried on a porous plate. The filtrate was worked up for further quantities of coumarins following essentially the method of Späth and Socias (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 59), thus :

The oil was cooled to about 15° and to it was added 200 c.c. of 20% methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide with constant shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand for 45 minutes, at the same temperature and then poured into 1.5 litres of ice-water. The mixture was then extracted with ether. The aqueous portion was acidified with hydrochloric acid (congo. red) and distilled in vacuum to remove the greater portion of methyl alcohol and allowed to stand overnight. The separated oil was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was twice washed with 100 c.c. of 25% aqueous potassium carbonate solution and then with water. The ether layer was then dried over sodium chloride and the solvent removed. The residue solidified on keeping in an ice-chest for a few days. This was washed with petroleum ether and dried over a porous tile to remove adhering oil (Fraction R).

Purification of Fraction P: Isolation of Xanthotoxin.—This fraction was washed with cold 90% methyl alcohol to remove tarry matters. The crystalline residue was then repeatedly crystallised from alcohol and finally from benzene-petroleum ether, till the m.p. became constant at 145°. For analysis a portion was distilled at 140-45°/0.05 mm. and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether. (Found : C, 66.43; H, 4.00; OMe, 14.40. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.70; OMe, 14.35 per cent). The yield amounted to nearly 2.3 g. Mixed with a specimen of pure xanthotoxin, m.p. 145°, there was no depression of melting points.

Isolation of Luvangetin.—The Fraction Q and the Fraction R were mixed together and twice crystallised from hot methyl alcohol when pale yellow crystals (Fraction S) were obtained. The mother liquors gave on slow evaporation transparent plates and soft needles along with a little oily matter. The mixture was collected, washed with a little cold 80% methyl alcohol, and recrystallised from methyl alcohol very slowly. The plates and

needles, which separated out, were collected, washed with a little cold methyl alcohol and then separated from each other mechanically. The plates and needles were then crystallised separately from the same solvent, when 0.2 g. of xanthotoxin (needles), m.p. 144°, were obtained. The plates are those of luvangetin and had m.p. 107.8°.

The Fraction S was repeatedly crystallised from pure methyl alcohol when pale yellow opaque crystals, m.p. 121° (Fraction X) were obtained. The mother-liquors were allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature in separate vessels, when transparent plates mixed with varying quantities of opaque crystals separated. These were freed from the mother-liquor (Fraction Y) which was kept for further investigation. These were separated from each other by hand picking and the two varieties were crystallised separately in a similar manner. This operation took a considerable time. The transparent four-sided plates were then distilled at 145.55°/0.03 mm. (a small fraction distilling below 140° was rejected). The colourless distillate soon solidified and was recrystallised from acetone-petroleum ether, m.p. 108°. Recrystallisations from alcohol, ether or chloroform-petroleum ether did not raise the m.p. The substance is easily soluble in hot alcohol, chloroform, acetone, acetic acid and hot benzene. From benzene luvangetin separates as colourless plates, m.p. 102.4°. This substance when dried in vacuum over phosphorous pentoxide suffered a loss in weight, became opaque and the m.p. rose to 108°. Apparently luvangetin crystallises from benzene with benzene of crystallisation. (Found in sample dried in vacuum at 80°: C, 69.85, 69.63; H, 5.22, 5.44; 5.47; OMe, 11.76. M.W. by Rast's method in camphor, 242. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.73; H, 5.42; OMe, 12.02 per cent. M.W., 258). The yield of pure luvangetin amounted to 2.0 g.

Isolation of Xanthyletin from the Fraction (X).—The opaque crystals (*vide supra*) were distilled in vacuum at 130.40°/0.03 mm. and twice crystallised from acetone-ether, when colourless stout rhombic crystals, m.p. 128° (yield 0.1 g.) were obtained. (Found: C, 73.25; H, 5.47; M.W. by Rast's method in camphor, 232. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.68; H, 5.26; M.W. 228). The substance on catalytic hydrogenation yields a tetrahydro derivative, m.p. 158° which showed no depression in m.p. with tetrahydroxanthyletin, m.p. 158°.

Isolation of IsoPimpinellin from the Fraction Y.—The solids separated from the fraction Y (*vide supra*) were repeatedly crystallised from different solvents when the m.p. could not be raised above 151.152°. Mixed with a specimen of isopimpinellin it showed no depression in m.p.

Action of Acetic Anhydride on Luvangetin.—Luvangetin (0.1 g.) was boiled with 3 c.c. of acetic anhydride and 9.5 g. of freshly fused sodium acetate for 4 hours. The mixture was poured into cold water, neutralised with sodium bicarbonate and extracted with ether. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was crystallised from ether. m.p. 107.8°. No depression was observed on mixing with pure luvangetin.

Action of Oxalic Acid on Luvangetin.—Luvangetin (0.2 g.) and oxalic acid in 7 c.c. of water were boiled under reflux for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled and the crystals extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was dried over sodium chloride, concentrated and diluted with petroleum ether, when colourless crystals, m.p. 107.8°, were obtained. Mixed with luvangetin, the m.p. was found to be the same.

Action of Dilute Alkali on Luvangetin.—Luvangetin (0.1 g.) and pure methyl alcohol (5 c.c.) was mixed with 40 c.c. aqueous 1% potassium hydroxide and the solution was refluxed on the water-bath for half an hour. The yellow solution gradually became brown. It was

acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, kept overnight and extracted with ether. The residue from the ethereal solution was distilled in high vacuum ($140-45^{\circ}/0.03$ mm.) and crystallised from ether. The plates melted at 108° alone or mixed with a pure specimen of luvangetin.

Attempts to dehydrogenate Luvangetin with Palladium Black.—(a) Luvangetin (0.2 g) was heated with palladium black (0.6 g.) for 4 hours at $100^{\circ}-2^{\circ}$ in vacuum (2 mm. pressure). Distillation of the product in vacuum ($140-45^{\circ}/0.03$ mm.) gave a liquid distillate, which on crystallisation from acetone-petroleum ether melted at 108° and was identified as luvangetin by the mixed m.p. method. (b) A similar experiment was carried out at 180° under ordinary pressure for 8 hours. In this case too unchanged luvangetin was recovered in a yield of over 80%.

Oxidation of Luvangetin by Alkaline Hydrogen Peroxide.—Luvangetin (0.1 g.) was dissolved in aqueous potassium hydroxide (10 c.c. 5%) and 5 c.c. of 8% hydrogen peroxide added. The mixture was left for 15 hours and then heated on the water-bath to decompose the excess of H_2O_2 . The solution was cooled, just acidified with hydrochloric acid and made faintly alkaline with ammonia. Addition of a few drops of calcium chloride precipitated calcium oxalate which was filtered off. The clear filtrate was again acidified with hydrochloric acid and thoroughly extracted with ether. The residue from the dry ethereal solution did not crystallise. Distillation in high vacuum did not give any fraction which could be crystallised.

Catalytic Hydrogenation of Luvangetin.—Luvangetin (0.2 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol, (10 c.c.) was shaken with 0.1 g. of 25% palladium-charcoal catalyst (which had been previously saturated with hydrogen) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. 175 C.c. of hydrogen were absorbed within a few minutes at 22° and 766 mm. ($C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires 18.4 c.c. at 22° and 766 mm.). The solution was freed from the catalyst and the solvent removed. The resulting crystalline mass was distilled at $140-50^{\circ}/0.04$ mm. The distillate (0.2 g.) was crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether when shining plates, m.p. 131° , were obtained. (Found: C, 69.55; H, 6.38; OMe, 11.02. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.15; OMe, 11.92 per cent). It gave a yellow solution with cold concentrated sulphuric acid.